

Fig. 2. Changes in fluorescence spectra of 9, 10 DPA on adding Tween-20 in 30% ethanolic medium.

$\lambda_{ex} = 364 \text{ nm}$
 ●—● 9, 10 DPA ($10^{-6} M$)
 ○—○ 9, 10 DPA with 0.005% Tween-20
 ×—× 9, 10 DPA with 0.300% Tween-20.

Enhancement in fluorescence intensity on addition of non-ionic, anionic and cationic surfactants as well as on addition of ethanol are indicated in Fig. 3. It can be observed that large and sudden

Fig. 3. (i) Variations in fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA in 20% ethanolic medium

($\lambda_{ex} = 364 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{em} = 412 \text{ nm}$).
 (A) Varying the concentration of Tx-100
 (B) Varying the concentration of DBSS
 (C) Varying the concentration of CTAB

(ii) (D) Influence of ethanol concentration on the fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA.
 cmc values are marked by arrow \otimes →.

increase in fluorescence intensity occurred near the cmc of the surfactant.

These observations can be explained on the basis of solubilizing action of the surfactants and also of ethanol. The enhancement in the fluorescence intensity on the addition of surfactant in 20% and 30% ethanolic medium appears to be due to the solubilization of 9, 10 DPA in the surfactant micelle since large enhancement in fluorescence intensity occurs in the cmc region of the concerned surfactant.

It appears that 9, 10 DPA is not fully solubilized in 20% ethanolic medium, since the fluorescence intensity reaches a limiting value only in presence of 50% or higher ethanolic concentration. The diminished effect of the surfactant in presence of higher ethanolic concentration is due to the destruction of surfactant micelle⁶⁻⁸.

The shape of fluorescence spectra remains unchanged during the addition of surfactants or ethanol. This indicates that the molecules of 9, 10 DPA undergo no change in size or geometry during these processes and only solubilization of the colloidal particles occurs during these reactions.

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Note on the Separation of 2 : 4-Dinitrophenol and Picric Acid by Column Chromatography

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IN a previous communication, the authors¹ have reported on the development of anion-exchange properties of Brockmann alumina, on pretreatment with HCl acid at low pH values ($pH < 5.5$). It was

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shown that picric acid and 2:4-dinitrophenol (2:4-DNP) from benzene solution are strongly sorbed by alumina (pH 3.2-5.5) but desorbed to varying extents with dioxane-water (4:1, v/v). In the present communication, we have examined the column chromatography of the solutes.

The earlier studies by other workers^{2,3,4} do not appear to have incorporated the systematic studies on the binary separation of the solutes from their synthetic mixture using Brockmann alumina.

Procedure :

Glass Column (25×1 cm) was packed dry with Brockmann alumina of pH 5.5 to a column height of 16 cm. The solutes (BDH) were recrystallised as described earlier¹, and dissolved in purified benzene (80 mg/l). 5-ml solutions were withdrawn, mixed, applied to the column, and kept as such for an hour. 2:4-DNP was eluted with 40 ml of dioxane-water (4:1) followed by picric acid with 20 ml of dioxane-acetate buffer solution of pH 5.5 (1:1, v/v). The two eluates were examined for their identity by spot test with aq KCN⁵. Eluate fractions were determined colorimetrically by developing colour with alkali, as described previously¹.

The distribution coefficients (K_d) from benzene solution were found to be as follows :

2:4-DNP...17.6, and Picric acid...32.6.

The recoveries were 99.9%.

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Oxidation of Hydrocarbons. Part II. Catalytic Oxidation of Paraffin Wax at 413°K

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THE study of oxidation of hydrocarbons has been of considerable interest for several workers¹⁻⁸. The importance of these studies is twofold. Firstly, the oxidation products have found numerous applications such as their usefulness in the manufacture of detergents, synthetic fibres, plastics and

several good quality solvents. Secondly, these studies help to understand the mechanism of these reactions.

We have undertaken a systematic study of catalytic oxidation of hydrocarbons in liquid phase. In part-1 of this series⁸ we reported kinetics of the catalytic oxidation of liquid-paraffin. The present work reports liquid phase catalytic air-oxidation of paraffin wax at 413°K. Five different cobalt salt catalysts used are cobalt naphthenate(I), cobalt bromide(II), cobalt carbonate(III), cobalt chloride (IV), and cobalt sulphate(V). Attempts have also been made to study the effects of amount of catalyst and rate of air-flow.

Experimental

Chemicals : Paraffin wax (L.R.) used had congealing point 331-333°K. Cobalt naphthenate, cobalt bromide, cobalt carbonate, cobalt chloride and cobalt sulphate (each L. R. grade) were used as such.

Method : The apparatus and the procedure used were similar as reported in part-1⁸. The temperature of oil-thermostat was kept at 413°K±0.1°. The air supply through the sample was maintained at the rate of 8.8 litres/minute (unless otherwise mentioned).

Results and Discussion

In Figure 1 plots of acid values against time have been given. Catalyst concentration in each case was

Fig. 1. Catalytic Effect of some Cobalt Salts on the Carboxylic Acid Formation using 0.400% (w/v) Catalyst at 413°K.

- Δ— Cobalt Carbonate
- Cobalt Bromide
- Cobalt Naphthenate
- ×— Cobalt Chloride
- Cobalt Sulphate
- ×— Without Catalyst